

Meeting Summary

The Global Geodetic Observing System (GGOS) of the International Association of Geodesy (IAG) convened geodetic and geophysical communities to participate in the *GGOS Topical Meeting on the Atmosphere, held in Potsdam, Germany, 7-9 October 2024*. The main objectives were a general brainstorming and in-depth discussions on the challenges and opportunities of integrating geodetic and geophysical technologies for a comprehensive monitoring of the lower atmosphere (i.e. troposphere and stratosphere), the mid atmosphere (mesosphere) and the upper atmosphere (incl. thermosphere, ionosphere and plasmasphere), as well as the identification of existing techniques and potential new applications leading to operational generation, dissemination and societal use of products in this important and highly up-to-date research area. This Topical Meeting was organised as a main activity of the project *Characterisation of the Ionised Atmosphere in terms of Essential Variables* granted by the International Union of Geodesy and Geophysics (IUGG) for 2024/2025 with the support of the International Association of Geomagnetism and Aeronomy (IAGA) and the IAG. IAGA's main contribution is the high level of knowledge, understanding and geophysical modelling of the physical processes that govern the Sun's influence on the atmosphere, while IAG's contribution is based on the detection and mathematical modelling of the impact of these processes on geodetic measurements. As almost all geodetic observations are affected by the atmosphere in various ways, geodesists need on the one hand side to model, quantify, understand and correct these effects, but are on the other hand side able to provide a huge amount of valuable and highly accurate information on the state and the dynamics of the atmosphere.

Alongside the hydrosphere and the geosphere, the atmosphere is one of the most important components of the Earth system. In geodetic Earth system research and modelling, we aim on a highly accurate knowledge of the dynamical processes within and between the individual components and subcomponents (in the case of the atmosphere, these are, e.g., the troposphere, stratosphere, thermosphere, ionosphere and plasmasphere, embedded by the magnetosphere). The highly accurate information from geodetic observation techniques will be strongly support the realisation of this task. The results will not only improve our knowledge of the Earth system, but also provide the reliability that users expect for modern high-precision applications such as autonomous driving or precision farming.

The meeting was attended by 76 participants from 21 countries. 36 participants are early career scientists. Thanks to the generous support of the IUGG, the IAG and the IAGA, travel grants were provided to six colleagues to enable them to attend the meeting. Contributions covered topics from

- GGOS Focus Area “Geodetic Space Weather Research - GSWR”
- GGOS Focus Area “Artificial Intelligence for Geodesy – AI4G”

- GGOS Focus Area “Geohazards Monitoring”
- IAGA Interdivisional Commission on “Space Weather”
- IAGA Division II “Aeronomic Phenomena”
- IAGA Division V “Geomagnetic Observatories, Surveys and Analyses”
- IAG Commission 4 “Positioning and Applications”
- IAG Sub-Commission 4.3 “Atmospheric Remote Sensing”
- GGOS Study Group “AI for GNSS Remote Sensing”
- IAG Working Group “Remote sensing using GNSS reflected signals”
- Study Group “High-resolution probing of the Troposphere and Ionosphere” of IAG Inter-Commission Committee on Theory

Participants of the GGOS Topical Meeting on the Atmosphere, Potsdam, Germany, 7-9 October 2024 (Photo R. Heinkelmann)

The meeting opened with a *welcome address* by the President of GGOS, Laura Sánchez, Deutsches Geodätisches Forschungsinstitut (DGFI-TUM), Technische Universität München, and two keynote presentations: *GNSS remote sensing: Innovative Earth Observation with Great Perspectives* by Jens Wickert, Helmholtz Centre Potsdam - GFZ German Research Centre for Geosciences, and *Possible Definition of Essential Variables for the Upper Atmosphere from the Perspective of the Focus Area "Geodetic Space Weather Research"* by Michael Schmidt, DGFI-TUM, lead of the GGOS Focus Area GSWR. These two magistral presentations set the framework for the agenda of the meeting. 56 contributions, 36 oral and 20 posters, were distributed in the following sessions:

- Session 1: *Magnetosphere, Ionosphere, Plasmasphere and Thermosphere, as a coupled system*, convener Michael Schmidt, DGFI-TUM, Germany
- Session 2: *Ionosphere modelling and applications*, convener Paweł Wielgosz, University of Warmia and Mazury in Olsztyn, Poland
- Session 3: *Climate application of geodetic atmospheric parameters*, convener Rosa Pacione, C.S.M. Data Analysis Services, e-Geos/ASI-Centro di Geodesia Spaziale, Italy
- Session 4: *Geohazards monitoring*, convener Michela Ravanelli, Sapienza University of Rome, Italy
- Sessions 5 and 6: *Geodetic Methods for Water Vapor Monitoring and Severe Weather*, convener Kyriakos Balidakis, Helmholtz Centre Potsdam GFZ German Research Centre for Geosciences, Germany

- Session 7: *Atmospheric modelling based on artificial intelligence*, convener: Benedikt Soja, ETH Zurich, Switzerland.

In Session 1, the presentations covered the whole chain from the Sun to the Earth, including the subcomponents (subsystems) magnetosphere, ionosphere, plasmasphere and thermosphere (i.e. the MIPT system). Particular emphasis has been placed on coupling processes, i.e. the interactions between the subcomponents, advanced thermosphere modelling to improve consistency between observations and new applications, improved mass density estimation of physical models in the thermosphere using data assimilation, identification and modelling of regular patterns in the solar wind impact on the ionosphere, and estimation of the topside ionosphere and plasmasphere using sophisticated mathematical algorithms. The integrated modelling of the coupling processes within the MIPT system poses the major challenge for the near future in this area.

Highlights of Session 2 included the quality assessment of the Real-Time Global Ionosphere Maps (RT-GIMs) produced operationally by the International GNSS Service (IGS), the use of low-Earth orbit satellite constellations for electron density (Ne) modelling and vertical profile reconstruction, including the simulated application of Inter-Satellite Links (ISL) measurements, validation of ionospheric models using GNSS Ionospheric Radio Occultation (IRO) measurements, detection and three-dimensional (3D) imaging of low latitude plasma bubbles, advances in near real-time and post-processing of global Rate of TEC (Total Electron Content) Index (ROTI) maps, and State Space Representation (SSR) ionospheric corrections to improve Precise Point Positioning (PPP) at low latitudes. Challenges for the near future focus on the quality assessment and optimal combination of multi-GNSS data for the generation of the IGS RT-GIMs, the operational generation of global ROTI maps, and the implementation of related real-time warning services for positioning (enhanced risk information), the establishment of a standard for the validation of ionospheric models with IRO measurements, and the exploration of machine learning algorithms for the prediction of ionospheric parameters.

Impressions from the Early Career Scientist Meeting at the GGOS Topical Meeting on the Atmosphere (Photos J. Koch)

In Session 3, the presentations provided an update on recent progress in the contribution of geodesy to climate monitoring, in particular to the atmospheric Essential Climate Variables (ECVs) defined by the Global Climate Observing System (GCOS) of the World Meteorological Organisation (WMO). A major focus was on improving the reliability of Integrated Water Vapour (IWV) estimates with ground-based GNSS and VLBI. These two techniques can provide the climate community with high-frequency, all-weather, long-term, homogeneously processed, global or denser regional, independent data sets of tropospheric delays, IWV and horizontal gradients, which can be assimilated and used to validate and improve climate models (IWV, humidity, precipitation, temperature) and to study the spatial and temporal variations of water vapour (long-term, diurnal, seasonal cycles, etc.). It was also shown how GNSS is an essential technology for the implementation of the GCOS Reference Upper-Air Network (GRUAN), which requires the co-location of GNSS stations with radiosondes to provide long-term, high quality climate data sets from the surface through the troposphere to the stratosphere. The next challenges to be addressed focus on the reliable combination of tropospheric parameters mapped by all geodetic techniques (i.e. GNSS, VLBI, DORIS, etc.), data access and sharing to increase spatial resolution and global coverage, ensuring sustainability, quality and continuity through operational services capable of processing large amounts of current and historical data, and multidisciplinary research by bringing together geodesists and climatologists.

Session 4, dedicated to geohazard monitoring, focused on hazards from the ground (earthquakes, tsunamis) and from space (ionospheric scintillations). Different types of observations such as ground-based GNSS TEC, SWARM, ROTI, GNSS reflectometry (GNSS-R) with study cases in the Pacific and the Arctic were presented, with emphasis on the automatic and near real-time detection of imminent hazards through machine learning and filter analysis. A prominent example of this is the VARION (Variometric Approach for Real-Time Ionosphere Observation) algorithm, which is able to estimate TEC variations in real time and can be used to shed light on the mechanism of the lithosphere-atmosphere-ionosphere couplings and thus be used for ionospheric monitoring of natural hazard events. Another interesting presentation was dedicated to the GUARDIAN system of NASA's Jet Propulsion Laboratory (JPL), which aims to use near real-time GNSS TEC data to enhance natural hazard early warning systems. The GUARDIAN system is the first global, high-rate, multi-GNSS system for near-real-time ionospheric monitoring, and the main current effort is the implementation of automated detections using deep learning and convolutional neural networks.

Session 5 emphasised the importance of integrating different geodetic techniques for comprehensive water vapour monitoring and improving the accuracy of atmospheric measurements. Presentations covered the combination of estimates from different geodetic techniques, such as GNSS and VLBI, with data from Water Vapor Radiometers (WVR) to monitor atmospheric water vapour, showing how geodetic methods can provide high temporal and spatial resolution data on water vapour content, which is crucial for weather forecasting, climate studies and improving the accuracy of geodetic measurements affected by atmospheric delay. The case studies presented during the meeting aimed to assess the consistency and reliability of precipitable water vapour measurements using WVR (ground-based instrument measuring microwave signals affected by water vapour), GNSS (monitoring signal delays caused by atmospheric moisture), radiosondes (balloon-borne sensors measuring temperature, humidity and pressure) and ERA5 (a reanalysis dataset combining model and observational data).

Session 6 was dedicated to the use of geodetic techniques for severe weather monitoring and forecasting. The various presentations demonstrated the growing role of GNSS and other geodetic techniques in this field by providing real-time data on atmospheric conditions that can be integrated into weather models and forecasting systems. A key topic of discussion was the challenging combination of real-time GNSS data with radar reflectivity measurements as complementary data that can improve the detection, analysis and tracking of severe weather

events such as thunderstorms or heavy precipitation. Another presentation gave an insight into the use of GNSS signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) measurements to track severe thunderstorms. SNR variations can indicate changes in atmospheric conditions, such as water vapour content, associated with storm development. Case studies from Central Europe in the summer of 2023 illustrate how GNSS-SNR data can be used for real-time monitoring of severe weather events. Finally, GRENet (GNSS-Enhanced Radar Extrapolation Network for Precipitation Nowcasting) was presented as a successful example for the integrated analysis of GNSS data with radar-based precipitation measurements to improve short-term weather forecasts (nowcasting).

Section 7 highlighted the application of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) techniques to atmospheric modelling, addressing various challenges and opportunities in understanding and predicting atmospheric behaviour. Some presentations demonstrated how AI techniques can analyse large data sets, identify complex patterns and make predictions about atmospheric conditions such as temperature, humidity, wind patterns and air quality. Other presentations showed how AI-based models can also help improve weather and climate forecasts by learning from historical data. Despite the strong performance of AI techniques in atmospheric modelling, several challenges remain. For example, AI models, especially deep learning models, are often considered as "black boxes" because their decision-making processes are not or at least not easily understandable. To improve the interpretability and confidence, methods such as feature importance analysis, uncertainty quantification, and model explainability tools need to be further developed. In addition, the success of AI models depends heavily on the quality of the input data. Poor data quality can lead to inaccurate predictions. Therefore, a key recommendation of this session is that data inspection, cleaning and pre-processing are critical steps in AI-based atmospheric modelling.

Impressions from the GGOS Topical meeting on the Atmosphere, (Photo R. Heinkelmann)

More information at

- Presentations: <https://zenodo.org/communities/ggos-topical-meeting-atmosphere/>
- Event website, meeting summary and photos: <https://ggos.org/event/ggos-topical-meeting-atmosphere/>.

In addition to the technical sessions, a guided tour through the emblematic facilities of the GFZ was organised and a "come together" for all participating young scientists took place. This event was not only restricted to the GGOS Topical Meeting on the Atmosphere, but also included the GRACE/GRACE-FO Science Team Meeting 2024, which took place at GFZ from 4 to 8 October, and the GGOS Days 2024, which followed the Topical Meeting on October 10 and 11. This informal "come together" meeting was sponsored by the IAG and was attended by about 45 young colleagues who had the opportunity to get to know each other, to talk about their work, and to network. We would like to take this opportunity to thank Ludwig Grunwaldt and Christoph Förste

from GFZ for the warm welcome and interesting explanations during the visit to GFZ, as well as Julia Koch, PhD student at ETH Zurich, who, as GGOS Early Career Representative, organised the event with the young colleagues.

Overall, we can say that the GGOS Topical Meeting on the Atmosphere was very successful. As it was not as large and long as the usual international geoscience conferences, the participants were very much focused and, with time to discuss topics of interest in detail, it was possible to have a sensible and friendly exchange of views that will undoubtedly help to advance the combination and integrated analysis of geodetic and geophysical measurements for modelling the atmosphere, from the Earth's surface to the plasmasphere. During the workshop, the desire was repeatedly expressed to hold such meetings more frequently and as regularly as possible in future in order to monitor progress and find new ways to overcome new challenges. In particular, the highly accurate and reliable geodetic and geophysical observations should be brought in and combined to further advance the modelling of the atmosphere and achieve the ambitious goals of an improved understanding of the Earth system. The future realisation of this kind of meetings will be considered by GGOS and its Focus Areas.

The GGOS Topical Meeting on the Atmosphere was only possible thanks to the support of numerous colleagues who defined the topics of the meeting, chaired the sessions, gave presentations and participated in the discussions.

Special thanks go to GFZ Potsdam for hosting the meeting and to the local organising committee: Kirsten Elger, Robert Heinkelmann, Nataliya Bobenko, Sascha Torkhov and Alexander Brauser. Their tireless work ensured a familiar and comfortable atmosphere throughout the meeting. Special thanks are also due to the IUGG, whose support enabled the meeting to be held free of charge for all participants, thus facilitating the attendance of many colleagues, especially early career scientists. Finally, we would like to thank the Deutsches Geodätisches Forschungsinstitut of the Technical University of Munich (DGFI-TUM) and the Austrian Federal Office of Metrology and Surveying (BEV) for hosting and supporting the GGOS Presidency and the GGOS Coordinating Office, respectively. This support is very much appreciated.

*Laura Sánchez, DGFI-TUM, President of GGOS
Michael Schmidt, DGFI-TUM, Lead of the GGOS Focus Area
“Geodetic Space Weather Research”
October 2024*